

Exploring Carpooling as a Viable Solution to Traffic Congestion in Ghana's Cities: A Case Study of Formal Sector Workers in Accra

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Abstract

This study sought to examine the willingness of formal sector workers in Accra to carpool. This is important as most private vehicle trips in the city are work-related. We adopted a case study research design with a purposeful sample of 150 private vehicle users drawn from three companies in Accra. The study participants drove to and from work using their private vehicles. The results of the standard multiple regression models indicated that the willingness to carpool is influenced by the sex, age, religion and monthly income.

Contrary to expectation, we found that the higher the participant's monthly income, the more willing the participant will be to carpool. However, religion was shown to positively influence carpooling. We affirm that as an attitude and behaviour reforming factor, religion has an important role to play in sustainable transport decision-making process and thus should be prioritised in future travel behaviour studies. We recommend that strategies to institutionalise carpooling among formal sector workers in the city should take into consideration their socio-demographics. We strongly believe carpooling may be the viable option in achieving long-term traffic congestion relief in Accra. Further, we are convinced the establishment of "carpool clubs", route-and-schedule-based carpool matching services, and the institutionalisation and enforcement of strict workplace parking restrictions are necessary for a sustainable workplace carpooling in Accra.

Keywords

Formal sector workers; carpooling; traffic congestion; Accra; private vehicles; workplace

Introduction

The global vehicle population over the past decades has increased steadily, from about 960 million in 2000 (Gorham et al., 2022), 1.056 billion in 2010 (Soprych et al., 2023), and currently about 1.6 billion, representing 1 vehicle in every 5 persons of the inhabitants of the earth (Nakhle, 2025). This is estimated to increase to about 2 billion by the year 2030 with a higher increase in BRICS countries (Martins et al., 2021; Soprych et al., 2023). There is a varying pattern across regions, in terms of the global motorization landscape. The projections for BRICS countries show saturation levels ranging from 290 cars per 1,000 population in India to about 730 cars per 1000 population in South Africa (Seum et al., 2020). Private vehicle ownership and use are also on the increase because of their perceived benefits especially perceptions on safety playing crucial roles in private vehicle ownership and usage (Jabbari et al., 2022; Moody et al., 2021). However, the upsurge in private vehicle use has brought negative externalities (social costs) in health, environmental and energy resources which impedes sustainable transportation.

The situation in Ghana is not different. The total number of registered vehicles as of 2022 stood at about 3.2 million (with 72% petrol, 27% diesel, and 1% LPG powered) (Peprah, 2023). The corresponding motorisation rate in 2022 is estimated at about 100 vehicles per 1,000 inhabitants, rising from earlier rates of roughly 70 per 1,000 in 2015 (Okafor et al., 2023). Most of these vehicles are private vehicles with implications for traffic congestion and traffic management, fuel consumption, productivity (loss of productivity hours in traffic), and air and noise pollution, especially at the urban centres. Related to this, a recent study in Ghana (Dzivon et al., 2025) found that informal public transport mini- and midi-buses (trotro vehicles) account for 59% of perceived contribution to traffic congestion, while private cars contribute 29%, indicating that congested roads in the country are private-car dominated. Several studies have shown that much traffic congestion occurs on arterials and urban streets (Alkaissi, 2024; Kelly & Gupta, 2024; Lieberthal et al., 2024; Mohammed, 2023; OECD, 2025).

The foregoing suggests that smart mobility concepts are needed to reduce or reverse the negative externalities associated with this automobile upsurge. One of the widely appreciated and workable smart mobility practice yet unexplored in most metropolitan cities in the developing countries

including Ghana is carpooling. Carpooling is a transportation demand management strategy aimed at encouraging people to share private cars in order to increase the occupancy and reduce the number of vehicles travelled (Chen et al., 2023). Similarly, as a smart transportation mode, carpooling optimises the movement of people and goods rather than vehicles by inducing travellers to use existing private cars at higher load factors (Anthopoulos & Tzimos, 2021). In this way, traffic congestion and its attendant energy consumption and environmental problems are reduced (Delgado-Fernández et al., 2024).

Carpooling is not a contemporary phenomenon since its needs have always accompanied the growth of cities and towns across the world for a long time. Formal carpool systems and car-sharing trials were indeed initiated in Europe in the late 1940s, and in America, the oil price shocks of the 1970s, necessitated the active promotion of carpooling (Furuhata et al., 2013; Jaybhaye et al., 2023; Kirthiga et al., 2024). Previous studies on carpooling have examined users' behaviour and preferences, and as Javid et al. (2017), Si et al. (2023), Le Boennec et al. (2024), Neoh et al. (2017) and Olsson et al. (2019) have shown. Such studies consistently focused on commuters' behaviour, preferences, and motivations to participate in carpooling. Nonetheless, there is still a knowledge gap about actual possibilities of carpooling and its role in curtailing transportation problems that saddle most cities in the developing countries. As observed by Javid et al. (2025), carpooling is still not a popular transportation alternative and is considered an informal and disorganised activity. For example, only 8.6% of U.S. workers carpoled to work in 2022, compared to 68.7% who drove alone (US Census Bureau, 2024).

The present study

Traffic jams in Ghanaian urban centers, especially in the cities such as Accra and Kumasi has been a major concern that is likely to deteriorate as the population and the number of vehicles on the road increases. The existing traffic management systems are weak and based on obsolete approaches that fail to optimise traffic flow, resulting in inefficiencies and excessive delays (Dapaah et al., 2022). The situation is likely to worsen in the near future as estimated by the Ghana National Spatial Development Framework, 2015-2035 (2015: p.20):

“Passenger traffic on the trunk roads is expected to grow faster (2.4% per annum) than the population, and air and rail facilities demands are expected to increase even faster than

road transport. However, it is unlikely that new infrastructure alone will be able to meet the demand for mobility; other measures will be needed including getting more out of the existing infrastructure, through better maintenance and demand management, and smart urban growth policies and reforms”.

Accra, the capital city of Ghana like many other cities in the world, is faced with acute transportation management problems. Besides the physical problems of poor nature of roads, there is vast vehicular traffic congestion (Adugbila et al., 2023; Agyapong & Ojo, 2018; Dapaah et al., 2022). Amanor et al. (2024) associated this heavy congestion in the capital city to over-concentration in road transportation to the neglect of other transport modes. However, Boateng & Klopp, (2022) claim that the increased private car ownership is the reason and that it can be attributed to government underinvestment in public transportation, and economic liberalisation policies that make it relatively easy to import cars. In Accra, private cars occupy approximately 75% of road space, significantly outweighing their modal share (OECD, 2025).

Furthermore, traffic jam is on a constant rise in the metropolis with consistent passenger complaints about how the situation impedes their daily activities. Many hours spent sitting in traffic causes frustration and discomfort for urban commuters. For this reason, it is common to see drivers flouting traffic laws such as jumping red lights, driving on shoulders of the road as well as using unapproved routes. These, however, have implications for road traffic safety (Acheampong et al., 2019; Harriet et al., 2013; Memon & Kumar, 2020).

The foregoing suggests that the traffic congestion problem in the Accra metropolis requires pragmatic interventions. As a result, carpooling that is aimed at encouraging people to share cars in order to increase the occupancy and reduce the number of vehicles travelled represents such an alternative to SOV use (Mitropoulos et al., 2021). Given the increasing number of private vehicles in Accra, carpooling will be a plausible strategy to reducing the heavy vehicular traffic congestion that saddles the capital city. Even though carpooling has been shown to have long-term traffic congestion reliefs in urban centres (Olayode et al., 2023), the question remains how willing are private vehicle users to carpool? In the light of this, the present study sought to examine the willingness of private vehicle users in Accra, Ghana to carpool. As a case study, this study sampled formal sector workers from three companies (two multinational corporations and one national) in

Accra. This was informed by the knowledge that formal sector workers, especially in the Ghanaian context, prioritise private vehicle ownership and use, and are more likely to drive alone (see (Andreasen et al., 2024; Zambang et al., 2021)).

In addition, the belief that workplaces (employers) play important roles in promoting carpooling (Chen & Yang, 2023; Esztergár-Kiss & Zagabria, 2025; Mitropoulos et al., 2021; Shaheen, 2019; Tscharaktschiew & Reimann, 2021) as most private car trips are to the workplace further justifies our focus on formal sector workers. This study uses the standard multiple regression techniques to examine formal sector workers' willingness to carpool as a function of their socio-demographics (sex, age, marital status, educational attainment, religion and monthly income), the motivation for using a private vehicle, previous ridesharing, motivation to carpool and perceived challenges of carpooling. We expect these variables to affect the willingness to carpool among formal sector workers. This expectation is informed by previous findings in related travel behaviour studies. Regarding the impact of socio-demographics on travel behaviour, We have found compelling evidence (including Chen & Yang, 2023; Mitropoulos et al., 2021; Player et al., 2023; Si et al., 2023; Zambang et al., 2021) to expect a significant influence on the willingness to carpool. For instance, Player et al. (2023) reviewed a number of studies on factors influencing travel behaviour and found some significant relationship between socio-demographics (sex, age, income) and travel behaviour.

Also, the motivation for using a private vehicle (e.g. autonomy/ privacy, convenience, reliability etc.) have also been shown to influence travel behaviour (see Si et al., 2023; Soza-Parra & Cats, 2024). These motivational beliefs may facilitate or encumber travel behaviour. Intuitively, a person who reveres autonomy may be unwilling to carpool or share a ride with others. However, a person who had once shared a ride (previous ridesharing) and is motivated to save cost (motivation to carpool) may be more willing to form carpools. Yet, we admit that the perceived challenges of carpooling may inversely affect carpool formation.

In this study, we sought to provide an empirical basis for the institutionalisation of carpooling, especially in workplaces and among formal sector workers, as a traffic demand management strategy in tackling traffic congestion in Accra. To the best of our knowledge, no study has been conducted on this in the country notwithstanding the need. Several definitions of carpooling have

been proposed (see Aguilera & Pigalle, 2021; Bachmann et al., 2018; Javid et al., 2025; Le Boennec et al., 2024). However, in this study, we defined carpooling as a travel arrangement by owners and drivers of private cars who agree to travel together with their neighbours who work in the same or close destinations to and/or from the workplace without any profit motive but may have cost saving or cost-sharing intentions.

Method and data

Research Design

The study employed the case study research design. The case study design is particularly useful when exploring an unknown phenomenon in order to offer a holistic understanding of its characteristics (Kumar, 2019; Sibbald et al., 2021; Yin, 2018). Particularly, as Merriam & Tisdell, (2016) argued, the case study design focuses more on insight, discovery, and interpretation than on hypothesis testing. As this study sought to examine the willingness of formal sector workers in Accra to carpool, a phenomenon less researched and practised in Africa, the case study design was the favoured approach,

Study area

Accra metropolis is the national capital and the foremost administrative and commercial centre of Ghana and for this study the data collection site. It is the most populous city in Ghana with an estimated population of 5.8 million as at 2025 (5,455,692 from 2021), increasing by 3.1% per annum. There are 69.3 persons per hectare on the average; however, in higher income areas, the figure may be quite low: between 17.5 and 40 persons per hectare. It has a total land area of 173 km². Accra attracts the largest share of the country's rural-urban migrants given the relative availability of employment, educational, health, and social facilities and opportunities. These invariably generate travel demand and consequently traffic (traffic is a function of land use and activities).

It must be noted that Accra is not the only Ghanaian city confronted with vehicular traffic congestion, as all major cities in Ghana including Takoradi, Kumasi, and Tamale have equally heavy vehicular congestion that needs to be investigated. However, Accra has the highest vehicle

population of 1,164,942 increasing by more than 10% per annum (SSATP / World Bank, 2018).

Figure 1 shows the patterns of roads in the city.

Fig. 1 Map of Accra metropolis

Source: Google Earth, 2025

Participants

The study participants comprised a sample of formal sector workers in Accra who commute daily to and from work using their private vehicles. As indicated earlier, three companies (out of the host of companies visited) granted permission for the survey of their relevant employees on the subject matter of the study. These companies; two multinational and one national were Mediterranean Shipping Company, Anglo-Gold.

Ashanti and Cocoa Marketing Control located in Adabraka, '37' and the Central Business District respectively. Table 1 gives a breakdown of the participants per each company relative to the total company employees, and the number owning and driving private vehicles to work. Given the nature of the topic, we employed purposive sampling procedures. Prior to the actual data collection, a reconnaissance survey of each organisation was conducted purposely to introduce the study and its objectives and also to solicit for participation in the study. During the actual data collection exercise, those who had consented to participate in the study were administered with questionnaires. A total of 150 employees (54 from Mediterranean Shipping Company, 49 from

AngloGold Ashanti and 47 from Cocoa Marketing Control) participated in the study. The choice of the purposive sampling technique was informed by the view that it is the most useful technique in studying a relatively unknown phenomenon (Kumar, 2019).

Table 1: Distribution of study participants

Company	Total employees	Employees with private vehicles / (study sample)	Employees without private vehicles	Company employed drivers	Company-owned vehicles
Mediterranean Shipping Company	81	67 (54*)	9	5	14 (13 private cars and 1 bus)
AngloGold Ashanti	94	71 (49*)	17	6	13 (9 private cars and 4 trucks)
Cocoa House	75	58 (47*)	13	4	9 (8 private cars and 1 minibus)

NB: * Number of employees who participated in the study

Data collection instruments

The data for the study was sourced from a field survey we conducted in the Accra metropolis on travel behavior and carpooling. Data was collected using self-administered questionnaires. The questionnaires were distributed to the sample and retrieved at an agreed retrieval time and/ or day. This was done in order not to disrupt participants' work schedules and also to give them ample time to answer the questions fully to minimise the tendency of answering arbitrarily without much thoughtfulness and sincerity. However, some questionnaires were completed and returned on the same day of distribution. Data collection occurred between 17 April and 1 May 2025. Aside from the questionnaire administration, we observed traffic situation in some parts of the city (Fig. 2) during different time periods (morning peak (7am-9am), evening peak (5pm-7pm) and off-peak (10am-4pm) and concluded that traffic congestion in Accra is private-vehicle induced. Also, we observed that the surveyed companies had free parking space for staff and clients. This, we argued, motivated private car usage among the staff (Table 1 confirms this assertion, given the number of staff who use private cars in each company as against those who do not). Using both questionnaire and observation enabled a broad capture of relevant features of this study than a single approach would have afforded (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). A 100% response rate was achieved owing to

the efforts invested in retrieving the administered questionnaires. However, some questionnaires had some omissions.

Analysis

Pre-data analysis activities included data entry and data cleaning. Data analysis was done using the IBM SPSS Statistics software version 24 and presented using frequency distribution tables. The standard multiple regression techniques were used to examine the participants' willingness to carpool (dependent variable) as a function of their motivation to use private cars, motivation to carpool, previous ridesharing, perceived challenges to carpooling and their socio-demographic characteristics (independent variables).

The choice of this technique was to evaluate how much unique variance in the dependent variable each independent variable will explain. Tables 3 and 4 presents the responses on these variables and the model results respectively.

Results and discussion

Respondent's socio-demographic characteristics

Out of the 150 respondents, 75.3% were males, with the remaining 24.7% being females. This differential may be explained by the variance in educational attainment (a precondition for employment in the formal sector) of both sexes. According to the Ghana 2021 Population and Housing Census General Report on Literacy and Education (Ghana Statistical Service, 2022), there are more educated males than females in Ghana. And with participants coming from Mediterranean Shipping Company Limited, Anglo-Gold Ashanti and Cocoa Marketing Control, where employment is conditioned on formal educational qualifications, males were in the majority by virtue of their relatively higher education. Also, with the focus on formal sector workers driving to work, the sex differential could further be explained by the fact that in Ghana, more males than females drive (see Boateng et al., 2022; Osei et al., 2025). Furthermore, the majority of the respondents were more than 30 years old (58.7%); had attained tertiary education (74%); and were married (51.3%) at the time of the survey. In addition, a greater proportion of the respondents were Christians (69.3%); earned a monthly income between GHC 1100 and GHC 2000 (48%) and commuted to work mainly from the Achimota area (34.7%).

Table 2: Participants’ socio-demographic characteristics

Variable		N (%)	Variable		N (%)
Sex	Male	113 (75.3)	Religion	Christian	104 (69.3)
	Female	37 (24.7)		Muslim	44 (29.3)
Age	18-30 years	62 (41.3)	Monthly income	Other	2 (1.3)
	Above 30 years	88 (58.7)		GHC100-500	11 (7.2)
Educational attainment	Basic	4 (2.7)	GHC600-1000	43 (28.7)	
	Senior School	35 (23.3)	GHC1100-2000	72 (48.0)	
	Tertiary	111 (74.0)	Above GHC 2000	24 (16.0)	
	High School	35 (23.3)			
Marital status	Single	57 (38.0)	Residence	Achimota	52 (34.7)
	Married	77 (51.3)		Kaneshie-Kasoa	46 (30.7)
	Co-habiting	12 (8.0)		Spintex	35 (23.3)
	Separated/divorced	4 (2.7)		West Airport	17 (11.3)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Participants’ willingness to carpool

Of interest to the study were respondents’ motivation to drive private vehicles (reasons behind commuting by private vehicles), previous ridesharing, trip purpose when the ride was shared, willingness to carpool, motivation to carpool, and perceived challenges to carpooling (Table 3). We observed that the perceived freedom associated with private car use (39.3%) was the basic reason underlying the participants’ motivation to drive private vehicles, corroborating previous findings (e.g., Macea et al., 2023; Soza-Parra & Cats, 2024). For example, Von Behren et al. (2020) found that the private car is a symbol of freedom and independence. Also of priority to them was the flexibility associated with private vehicle use (28%).

Further, we realised that a substantial number (87.3%) of the respondents had ever shared a ride. Probing further, we observed that the rides were shared almost equally on both personal/recreational (51.1%), and work-related (48.9%) trips. Perhaps, this may be an indication of their willingness to carpool. However, when asked about their actual willingness to carpool, we observed mixed reactions.

Even though a sizeable number were unwilling to carpool (40.6%), the majority (59.4%) were either willing (42.7%) or very willing (16.7%) to form carpools.

Table 3 further reveals that 44% of the respondents were willing to carpool in order to save the cost of travelling alone, which is consistent with both previous findings and intuition. It is common knowledge that the “rational” commuter will always seek to spend less (minimise cost) on a journey but maximises satisfaction, all other things being equal. Other motivations to carpool according to the study included reducing the number of SOVs on the road (reduction in traffic congestion), avoiding parking difficulties and for companionship.

Again, regarding the possible challenges in forming carpools - delays (40%) and the security implications of carpooling (31.3%) were cited as the likely constraints. On the security implications, Javid et al., (2017) and Si et al. (2023) reported that strong belief on personal security is an important disincentive for carpooling.

Table 3: Responses to predictor variables

Variable		N (%)	Variable		N (%)
Motivation to drive private car	Personal freedom (privacy)	59 (39.3)	Motivation to carpool	Companionship	14 (9.3)
	Flexibility	42 (28.0)		Avoid parking difficulty	27 (18.0)
	Poor public transport service	30 (20.0)		Cost saving	66 (44.0)
	Prestige attached to automobile use	19 (12.7)		Reduce SOV on the road (reduce traffic congestion)	43 (28.7)
Previous ridesharing	Yes	131(87.3)	Perceived challenges with carpooling	Inconvenient meeting point	43 (28.7)
	No	19 (12.7)		Possible delays	60 (40.0)
Trip purpose when ride was shared	Commuting to and from work/ work related	64 (48.9)	Security implications	47 (31.3)	
	Recreation/personal errands	67 (51.1)			
Willingness to carpool	Very willing	25 (16.7)			

Willing	64 (42.7)
Not willing	61 (40.6)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The standard multiple regression techniques were used to test whether the factors discussed above significantly affected the respondents' willingness to carpool. The regression output (Table 4) indicated the model explained 21.6% of the variance ($R^2 = .21$, $F(10,139) = 3.82$, $p < .001$) in the willingness to carpool.

It was found that participants' monthly income ($\beta = .32$, $p < .001$) and age ($\beta = -.24$, $p < .01$) made the strongest statistically significant contributions in explaining their willingness to carpool. In other words, the formal sector workers' willingness to form carpools is depending importantly on their monthly income and age. What is most striking from the result is that there is a positive relationship between monthly income and the willingness to carpool, meaning the higher the participant's monthly income, the more willing the participant will be to carpool. This is, however, counterintuitive and contradicts previous studies (e.g., Benita, 2020; Molina et al., 2020; Olsson et al., 2019) which have suggested that income is inversely related to carpooling. For instance, both Delgado-Fernández et al. and (2024) Olsson et al. (2019) reported that the basic motivation behind carpooling is economic (cost saving), rather than choice. A possible explanation for this surprising finding may be the relatively higher monthly income reported by the majority of the participants. This finding, therefore, needs to be interpreted with caution. We recommend further studies to ascertain the true influence of monthly income on carpool formation among formal sector workers. Further, the model predicted that carpooling is inversely related with age; implying that the younger the employee, the more willingly the employee will be motivated to carpool and vice versa. This may be explained by the fact that the younger age (≤ 35) tends to be more fun-seeking (carpooling entails fun- the fun of travelling together with other people) (Bachmann et al., 2018; Javid et al., 2017; Olsson et al., 2019) and invariably less concerned about privacy. In this way, fun-seeking and privacy are supposed to be inversely related, giving credence to our earlier statement that the person who reveres in privacy is more unlikely to carpool.

Moreover, sex also predicted willingness to carpool, making a statistically significant contribution to the model. In a previous study, Le Goff et al. (2022) studied the effects of identified gender (sex) on carpool formation, and observed that females are more likely than males to carpool. This is not surprising as females are more prudent and cost saving. Further, females are more likely than males

to espouse sustainable travel behaviours (Olsson et al., 2019). Regarding this, these recent reviews and empirical studies found that women are often more willing to forgo the car and are more environmentally concerned (concern about ecological issues and the environmental impact of transport modes). Invariably, these are issues central to the debate on carpooling. On the basis of these, recent authors have emphasised the need to focus on gender in car use-attitude research.

Remarkably, religion also has a positive relationship with the willingness to carpool. This is vital as religion affects both decision-making and behaviour, and involves an endorsement of authority, loyalty and concern for the ‘common good’ (i.e. what is praiseworthy) (Kelly et al., 2024). In this regard, religion is expected to reform lives, moral and make people act in more acceptable ways.

Table 4: Participants’ willingness to carpool

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE B</i>	β
Constant	1.070 (0.02, 2.11)	.529	
Motivation to drive private car	.082 (-0.02, 0.18)	.053	.124
Previous ridesharing	.207 (-0.14, 0.56)	.180	.089
Motivation to carpool	.024 (0.09, 0.14)	.062	.030
Perceived challenges to carpooling	.035 (-0.06, 0.13)	.051	.054
Sex	.362 (0.09, 0.63)	.136	.217**
Age	-.350 (-0.60, -0.09)	.127	-.240**
Educational attainment	-.175 (-0.39, 0.04)	.113	-.124
Marital status	.040 (-0.13, 0.21)	.088	.040
Religion	.254 (0.01, 0.49)	.123	.175*
Monthly income	.288 (0.14, 0.43)	.072	
			.327***
<i>R</i> ²		.216	
<i>F</i>		3.82	

Note. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$; $N = 150$

Even though we expected previous ridesharing, motivation to drive a private vehicle, perceived challenges to carpool and educational attainment to have played significant roles in willingness to carpool, the result (Table 4) shows otherwise. However, though not significant, the contributions of motivation to drive private vehicle and educational attainment (explaining 12.4% of the variance in willingness to carpool apiece) were impressive.

Conclusion and the way forward

In the study, we sought to provide an empirical basis for the possible institutionalisation of carpooling, especially in workplaces among formal sector workers, as a traffic demand management strategy in tackling traffic congestion in Accra. As a consequence of this, we investigated the willingness of formal sector workers to carpool. As stated earlier, this is important given that most private vehicle trips in the city are work-related and so carpooling by workers will improve the traffic situation in the city.

In this regard, we adopted a case study research design with a purposeful sample of 150 private vehicle users in three companies in Accra. The study participants drive to and from work using their private vehicles (participant selection criteria). The study findings gave a clear indication of the willingness of formal sector workers to form carpools. We found that willingness to carpool is influenced by participants' sociodemographic characteristics (sex, age, religion and monthly income). Contrary to expectation, we found that the higher the participant's monthly income, the more willing the participant will be to carpool. However, the fact that religion was shown to positively influence carpooling suggest the importance that should be attached to it in future travel behaviour studies. We affirm that as an attitude and behaviour reforming factor, religion has an important role to play in sustainable transport decision-making process and thus should be prioritised in future travel behaviour studies.

Thus, strategies to institutionalise carpooling among formal sector workers should take into consideration their socio-demographics, especially monthly income. As Benita, (2020) argued, this consideration will be beneficial in designing sustainable carpool programmes to bring SOV drivers on board. This notwithstanding, we recommend further studies to explore also the willingness of Ghanaian employers and organisations to institutionalise carpooling among their workforce as well as policies in place, if any, for this purpose. As noted previously, some employers and city authorities elsewhere (e.g. developed countries) have through appropriate policies, rewards and sanctions (e.g. pay-as-you-park policies etc.) promoted carpooling and other sustainable transportation modes.

Given the rise in private car use, especially for work-related trips, coupled with the inflexibility and inefficiency of the public transportation system (service quality concerns), We advocate for

the institutionalisation of carpooling as an alternative sustainable transportation mode to public transportation and as a viable solution to Accra's traffic congestion. We strongly believe carpooling may be the viable option in achieving long-term traffic congestion relief in Accra. However, there is the need to provide favourable conditions to minimise the perceived challenges of carpooling (as indicated by the study participants). This will mean dealing with the meeting place, security and possible delay concerns. Some studies have also raised the issue of "psychological barriers" associated with riding with strangers (see Julagasigorn et al., 2021). Even though We believe this may not be a concern with the company-based carpooling programme as the possible carpoolers may already be acquainted (i.e. colleagues), We still think this is worthy of consideration.

Also, we are convinced the establishment of "carpool clubs" (see Mitropoulos et al., 2021) and relevant carpool matching based on similar commute routes and schedules (see Xia et al., 2019) will help minimise the security, and place of meeting and delay concerns respectively and maximise the associated benefits of carpooling. This is from the background that "*a large proportion of commuters likely share a similar commute route and schedule (thus leading to rush hour traffic)*" (Xia et al. 2019, p.3); this the study findings (Table 1) confirm.

Fortunately, in Accra, the majority of the workplaces and government ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs) are located in the same enclave and thus presents the possibility of effective carpooling among them. In this regard, it is important for the government and the respective employers to establish the most appropriate carpooling matching models and services, using the various workplace intranet, social media sites or a specially designed website. Tackling these challenges will undoubtedly help promote sustainable carpooling among formal sector workers in Accra. However, for these interventions to be successful, employers should implement strict parking restrictions and sanctions on offending employees while rewarding compliant employees. Also, the city authorities should empower the workplaces to enforce these restrictions and also monitor the implementation of these restrictions.

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Appendix

Figure 2 Private car induced traffic congestion in Achimota, Accra